

Plastics Recycling from and for home appliances, toys and textile

The project will tackle the actual challenges for the management of the end-of-life thermoplastic materials and their recycling, and will also design novel schemes to enhance the circularity of future product. The aim is to ensure recycle consistent quality and safe use in product for home appliances, toys and textiles, showing that high-quality, unique materials made from such waste can be reused, both within the same and new supply chains and products.

The challenge:

Changing the **'waste problem=cost'** for the EoL disposer to a **'re-born product=value'**, which is **fully recycled and safe**, preserving the embedded value as it moves through the whole process, will be faced by the proposed methodology.

The target:

High-quality recyclates from plastic waste streams (PWS) by developing an easy-to-use methodology for sorting, sampling, tracing, recycling techniques, and analysis procedures of both PWS and recyclates.

Specific technological and strategic goals:

Goal 1

Development and demonstration of standard, robust and easy-to-use sampling and analysis procedures to ensure consistent recycle quality and safe products.

Goal 2

Development of methods for detection and separation of legacy additives in the plastics waste streams to ensure safe recycling of plastics containing such additives.

Goal 3

Development of methods for traceability of recyclates to allow the identification of the origin of recycled materials via digital information management, through marking technologies and blockchain approaches.

Goal 4

Development of methodologies to determine the degree of degradation of recycled materials and to foresee their end-of-life.

Funded by the European Union

More information at: www.precycling-project.eu